

Privacy versus Convenience: The extent of willingness to share data with smart home devices

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ABSTRACT

With the increase of smart home devices, the amount of data generated by consumers has increased exponentially in the last few years. This contains mostly personal data which companies make use of to further personalise their services. The question that arises is: to what extent are users willing to sacrifice privacy for more convenience when using smart home devices? By gathering more data about industry 4.0 and smart home devices, a survey was conducted to determine the opinion of Dutch consumers of age between 20 and 30. In this survey, the consumers were asked about their willingness to share personal data with companies, based on the brand image of the company and the convenience it gives them. This study contributes to research by providing insight into the aspects that make a person want to share data with companies through smart home devices.

Keywords

Privacy, Convenience, Smart Home Appliances, Data Protection

INTRODUCTION

There is an increasing trend in the number of smart home devices that Dutch consumers, between the ages of 20 and 30, purchase. The data these devices generate give companies the chance to create better and more personalised services, to increase their profits and to provide a more convenient product or service (Li, S., Tryfonas, T., & Li, H, 2016). However, existing literature shows that smart home devices are not always reliable and trustworthy. For instance, the several privacy issues regarding the virtual assistant Alexa (Chung, Lorga, Voas & Lee, 2017). Employees of Amazon would eavesdrop on consumers and by doing so gather more personal data, without their

consent (Kshetri, N. & Voas, J., 2017). By having insight into which data consumers are willing to share, companies can actively prevent hurting the relationship with the consumers.

Through this research, it will be investigated to what extent users are willing to sacrifice privacy for more convenience when using smart home devices. Thereby, it is important to recognise what kind of information users are knowingly willing to share with the companies of smart home devices. It will also be investigated to what extent the brand image of a company influences users and their willingness to share data and the perceived risks when users do not share data.

The results of this research will provide companies with insights into the amount of data that users are willing to share with them.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

As stated in the introduction, this research will investigate to what extent users are willing to sacrifice privacy for more convenience when using smart home devices. Moreover, it will also be investigated what role brand image has on the willingness to share data. In this paragraph, these topics will be narrowed down.

Smart Homes

A smart home is the application of Internet technology within a household. It combines several areas such as data collection, data communication, data storage, data analysis and software design (Hu, 2017). Therefore, smart home devices allow users to monitor and control a wide range of home appliances remotely and intelligently.

This Internet of Things (IoT)-based technology offers more efficiency and convenience to end-users so they can achieve a better quality of living (Ali & Awad, 2018).

As stated before, by connecting smart homes to the Internet, users can access and control their homes remotely at any time and from anywhere in the world. An increase in remotely accessible devices enables end-users to know and control a wide range of aspects in their homes like controlling the temperature or checking which device is switched on. This results in more convenience for consumers of smart home devices (Jose & Malekian, 2015).

Privacy and Smart Homes

Security experts have identified several concerns regarding smart home devices. These concerns include privacy risks as well as vulnerable and unreliable devices (such as malicious devices and company data collection). Previous research shows that major privacy concerns of security experts are not shared by end-users. The reason for lack of concern by end-users is the trust in the company that provides the smart home devices and believing their existing mitigation strategies to be sufficient (Zeng, Mare & Roesner, 2017). Other research shows that privacy is not a primary consideration in users' decisions to purchase smart home devices. Although, it did serve as a deterrent for some non-users (Lau, Zimmerman & Schaub, 2018).

Even though privacy does not seem to be a major issue regarding the adoption of remotely accessible smart home devices, it is unclear whether end-users are aware of the amount of data they are sharing with companies through such devices. Many IoT devices have always-on sensors that constantly monitor condensed details of users' physical environments and influence the devices' network communications. Passive network observers, such as internet service providers could analyse IoT network traffic to infer sensitive details about users (Apthorpe, Reisman & Feimster, 2017).

Brand image

As stated earlier, Dutch consumers have a certain trust in companies that make them neglectful of the risks that come with the sharing of personal data. This trust is also a big factor in the adoption of smart home devices (Lee, Yang & Zo), but some of these companies are accused of abusing or already abused the data of their customers (Kshetri, N. & Voas, J., 2017). This might contradict the earlier statement. Therefore, it raises the question if the brand image of a company influences the way Dutch consumers share their data with companies that provide them with their smart home devices and if these consumers are willing to share more of their data if the company had a greater brand image.

While the analysis of customer data becomes increasingly more important for data-driven

business models, at the same time, the customers' concerns regarding data privacy have to be addressed properly (Gimpel, Kleindienst, Nuske, Rau & Schmied, 2018). Many types of research that have been conducted on this matter only concentrate on a small scope of end-users in the U.S. (Zeng, Mare & Roesner, 2017). Hence, this research focuses on users and potential users of smart home appliances in the Netherlands. Specifically, users between the age of 20 and 30, since that is the most common group that uses smart home devices (Statista, 2017).

The problem statement of the research is stated as follows: *“To what extent are Dutch (potential) consumers between the ages of 20 and 30, willing to share personal data with remotely accessible smart home devices in exchange for increased convenience?”*

METHOD

The starting point of the research was the gathering of several papers related to industry 4.0. Academic journals, including the Elsevier and the Journal of Information, Technology were used as a source. The keywords that were used include data, industry 4.0, development and technology, privacy, convenience, and brand image. After several papers were analysed, the findings were discussed between the researchers. It was then decided that the research would focus on IoT. Now that there was a focus on the field of the research, the problem statement was defined.

Before finalisation of the problem statement, the researchers searched back and forth for substantial evidence that the topic was relevant and no earlier studies on this topic were conducted. After analysis of multiple recent papers and different Dutch newspapers, with regards to current trends in the field of IoT, it was found out that there were several concerns around an emerging technology called smart home devices. This served as the foundation of this research. Academic papers were analysed in the field of smart home devices and it was discovered that most research focussed on privacy and security issues from the company's perspective. The researchers found an unsubstantial number of studies conducted on what data companies could collect without harming their relationship with their customers, and how much personal data end-users were willing to provide, in exchange for better services and thus, sacrificing their privacy for more convenience. Finally, the researchers determined that this would be the main focus of the research.

Several papers were used to write a problem indication and statement. After these were formulated the research was further narrowed down with a relevant research question and sub-questions.

The first sub-questions were answered with the use of a literature study, to get a better understanding of the subject and the theory. This further helped to form several survey questions that were asked to Dutch consumers from the age category of 20 to 30. Conducting surveys enables the researchers to collect opinions of these consumers and also test their opinion on smart home devices. Additionally, and most importantly, it gave an insight into which data they were willing to share with companies, how much they value their privacy in exchange for convenience and if they were aware of how much data they were indirectly sharing.

By combining formerly conducted research with the results of the survey, it was possible to answer the research question. When the research question was answered, it became clear that it was still possible to perform further research on the topics of smart home devices and privacy concerns. This further research was outlined and lastly, the research was discussed.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

To answer the main problem statement, the study is subdivided into smaller topics of interest, which will jointly answer the main question. The research questions answered in the study are as follows:

R1: What is brand image and how is it measured?

R2: Do users trust that companies do not misuse their data (retrieved through smart home appliances)?

R3: Are users aware of the amount of data they share with companies (through smart home appliances)?

R4: Are users aware of which data are gathered about them (through smart home appliances)?

R5: Are users aware in which way(s) data are gathered about them (through smart home appliances)?

R6: To what extent are users willing to share their personal data with companies (through smart home appliances) for more convenience?

R7: How does brand image influence the amount of data users are willing to share (through smart home appliances)?

CONCEPTUAL MODEL

Smart home appliances learn about consumers by observing their habits, tendencies and

preferences as well as their environments (Weinberg, Milne, Andonova, & Hajjat, 2015). Learning is based on behaviours and phenomena in the natural, physical world as opposed to the online world (Weinberg et al., 2015). As mentioned before, smart home appliances create opportunities including improving access and control of devices, increasing efficiency, productivity and connecting technologies (Weinberg et al., 2015). However, the use of smart home appliances increasingly leads to privacy concerns as any potential consumer at the individual level must always balance costs (which are often hidden costs) against benefits. For instance, giving up personal data against increased functionalities (Ng-Kruelle, Swatman, Rebne, & Hampe, 2002). When balancing costs against benefits, consumers' willingness to share personal data is often influenced by the brand image of the organisation (Wang, 2019).

As stated in the previous paragraph, this research investigates to what extent consumers are willing to share personal data with remotely accessible smart home device for better and more personalised services. Additionally, we investigate the effect of an organisation's brand image on the willingness of consumers to share personal data. The relationships are illustrated in Figure 1: Conceptual Model.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

Convenience

Consumer's perception of convenience can vary from one setting to another; consequently, there are numerous definitions of the term. The very definition of "convenience" adopted in this research is the definition of Vannini and Taggart (2015). According to Vannini and Taggart (2015), "convenience" has become synonymous with lack of complications and with a lifestyle rendered easy by countless consumer products and services (Vannini & Taggart, 2015).

The definition is adopted since it represents best what smart home appliances bring to consumers. Smart home devices create greater

convenience by allowing consumers to manage multiple systems within their houses with just the touch of a finger, thus taking away complications. For instance, controlling the temperature from a distance takes away the complication of being physically at home to change it.

As shown in Figure 1, the willingness to share personal data is partially influenced by the degree of convenience. This relationship indicates that if convenience increases (by enabling real-time responses, improving access and control of devices, increasing efficiency and productivity and connecting technologies), the willingness to share data is greater; thus, a positive relationship.

Research from Keller (1993) states that brand image is seen 'as the perceptions about a brand as reflected by the brand associations held in consumer memory'. Several studies indicate that positive brand image leads to higher brand trust and customer satisfaction. Brand trust is defined as "the willingness of the average consumer to rely on the ability of the brand to perform its stated function" (Chaudhuri & Holbrook 2001, page 82). Brand trust is created when a company meets its promises to deliver quality products and services to their consumers (Nawaz & Usman, 2011).

Brand Image

In utilising brands, consumers develop subjective perceptions of how brands perform across a range of criteria, which they consider important for evaluation purposes. These perceptions are organised by a consumer into a succinct picture of the brand which will play a part in that consumer's computation behaviour (Blackwell, Engel, Miniard, & Rahman, 2017). This is considered a "brand image" (Blackwell, Engel, Miniard, & Rahman, 2017). Several studies indicate that positive brand image leads to higher brand trust and customer satisfaction. Brand trust is defined as "the willingness of the average consumer to rely on the ability of the brand to perform its stated function" (Chaudhuri & Holbrook 2001, page 82). Brand trust is created when a company meets its promises to deliver quality products and services to their consumers (Nawaz & Usman, 2011).

There are several techniques to measure brand image. Research from (Plumeyer, Kottemann, Böger & Decker) listed several techniques to measure brand image.

Likert scaling is a measurement technique which is simple to set up, administer and analyse, but could mean limited results (Hair et al 2009). Semantic differential scaling has the same benefits as Likert scaling and gives researchers the opportunity to rate positive and negative feelings towards brands, although it needs a quite extended

pre-study to make sure the scales cover the most important aspects of brand image. In-depth interviews give researchers the opportunity to deeper understand the motivation of the participants which often results into highly detailed data (Hair et al. 2009) but can have low generalizability and in-depth interviews are time-consuming (McCracken 1988). The constant sum-method has the benefit of gaining insight on the brand image per brand and in relation to other brands (Hair et al. 2011) however, can be quite complex for participants to understand (Iacobucci and Churchill 2010).

For the purpose of this study, a survey was held in order to measure the correlation between brand image and the willingness to share data. Within the methods that are available to measure brand image with surveys, we chose Likert scales as they show a clear distinction between five options. Methods like the constant-sum-method were not used because those often refer to measuring brand image of certain companies, where our study focuses on brand image in general.

Likert scaling was used in order to measure the effect of brand image on the willingness to share data. T

The perceived brand image, and thus brand trust, has an influence on the willingness of users to share personal data with companies through smart home appliances. When the perceived brand image of a company increases, the amount of trust in a company and thus the willingness to share information with a company goes up (Shih & Wang 2018). The use of business privacy policies also negatively influences the amount of perceived privacy risk. On the contrary, the relationship between the perceived privacy risk and the willingness to share information is negatively correlated and thus will users not share any data if they mistrust the company Myerscough, Lowe & Alpert (2006).

RESULTS

In this section, the following topics will be presented: the data cleaning process, an overview and a description of the data and finally the findings of the report which include the tested hypotheses that are shown in the conceptual model and the correlations between the variables. The survey questions are included in Appendix I.

Data Cleaning Process

In order to analyse the gathered data, MS Excel was used. Altogether, 26 survey responses were received.

To obtain a reliable dataset, the dataset was cleaned by removing some unusual responses and

outliers. Respondents who completed the survey within one minute are not considered reliable because they most likely did not think the questions through. Furthermore, a few outliers were detected using a scatter plot. Those respondents were also removed from the dataset. After the ‘cleaning’ procedure, a sample of 21 responses remained in the dataset.

Description of the Data

After cleaning the data, the statistics were generated. All respondents are between the age of 21 and 28. 73 percent of the respondents claimed to have smart home appliances. The residual 27 percent does not possess any smart home appliances. The second group is considered as potential users of small home appliances.

Findings

To test the hypotheses, the sample dataset was examined on correlations between variables using a two-tailed Pearson correlation test. Table 3 presents a summary of the hypotheses testing results.

One-third of the respondents do not mind sharing personal data with companies. Most of the respondents (40 percent), responded neutrally on this matter. Furthermore, almost 90 percent of the respondents (strongly) agree with the fact that providing personal data with companies has become an increasing part of modern life.

Following, the subject ‘security’ was discussed within the survey. Almost 90 percent of the respondents do not trust that companies will not resell their personal data. Although this was the result, the opinions about the worry of the security of personal data gathered by companies were equally divided.

Furthermore, the topic ‘sharing data in return for more convenience’ was addressed. 66 percent of the respondents (strongly) agree that there is no alternative, other than to provide personal data if you want to obtain the maximum functionalities of smart home devices. 60 percent of the respondents also do not bother sharing personal data, in return for improved services.

The survey included questions about the topic ‘relationship between brand image and willingness to share data’. Most respondents (58 percent are willing to share data with companies whose products or services they have used in the past, as can be noticed in Table 1.

I am willing to share more data with companies whose products or services I have used in the past.	
Strongly agree	34%
Agree	25%
Neutral	8%
Disagree	25%
Strongly disagree	8%

Table 1: Sharing data with past producers

Thirty-three percent is not willing to share data with those companies and 33 percent of the respondents would not share data with a company that they distrust, regardless of the service or product that they offer. The other 67 percent of the respondents were divided on this matter.

Lastly, questions were asked about the topic of sharing of data with smart home appliances.’ On this matter, 46 percent of respondents feel that they have little control over the data that they provide through smart home appliances. Most respondents are also concerned in a certain way about the frequency of data that they are sharing with companies as is shown in Table 2. The data that most respondents are willing to share with companies of home appliances (regarding smart ovens and smart thermostats) are user preferences and environmental factors. Respondents are most sceptical about sharing their location and motion.

How concerned are you about the frequency of sharing data with companies?	
A great deal	7%
A lot	20%
A moderate amount	33%
A little	33%
None at all	7%

Table 2: Concerns about sharing frequency

Correlations

After examining the sample dataset, the correlations between the variables were determined. The main observations will be defined in this section. There is a strong positive correlation (0.903) between ‘the willingness to share data with companies whose services were used in the past’ and ‘not minding sharing personal data in return for improved services’. Thus, when respondents have had a positive experience with a certain company in the past, they are also more willing to share their personal data with that company in the future.

The second main observation is between ‘having smart home appliances’ and ‘the feeling of control over the data you provide through household appliances. These two variables also have a strong positive correlation (0,619). It appears that respondents who have the feeling of control over their data are also more likely to purchase smart home appliances.

The last main observation is one between ‘thinking that there is no alternative than to share personal data if you want to obtain the maximum functionalities of smart home appliances’ and ‘willingness to share personal data with bigger companies rather than smaller companies. The strongly positive correlation between these two variables is 0.706.

Hypotheses	Content	Supported (Yes/No)
H1	Users are aware of the data they are sharing.	No
H2	Users are willing to share more data with smart home devices when the convenience increases (e.g. increased functionalities, ease of use, less perceived risks).	Yes

H3	Brand image does influence the amount of data users are willing to share with their smart home devices.	Yes
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Table 3: Results Hypothesis Tests

DISCUSSION

This research contributes to the existing literature in multiple ways. First, the research fills the gap in the availability of current literature on the willingness of Dutch consumers to share personal data in exchange for more convenience. The topic had not earlier been researched extensively, and can, therefore, be considered a basis from which further research could be triggered. Partially because smart home appliances, which allow companies to gather large amounts of data (big data), are relatively new and upcoming. The implications and results on the long-term are still to be monitored and researched.

The insights provided in this report could contribute to academia, managers within companies which deal with the great amount of data that is shared with them through various ways, as well as consumers of smart home appliances. In practice, managers could use the outcomes of the research to assist them in making (strategic) decisions concerning data retrieval. If managers, for instance, learned that users are unaware of the data they are sharing, they could take action to address this. Dutch consumers, on the other hand, could gain insight into the ways and frequency of data they are sharing with companies.

The results of the survey indicate that only on two subjects almost all respondents agree, whereas the results from the other questions differ. The results do, however, indicate that the hypothesis which states that users are aware of the data they are sharing, is not true. Furthermore, the findings show that Dutch consumers between the ages of 20 and 30 are willing to share more data in exchange for more convenience and that they are influenced by a firm’s brand image. This provides new knowledge to existing literature. Nevertheless, the researchers of the study acknowledge that the results of the study are not highly generalisable to the target population. The results of the study are quite apart from each other; thus, it is hard to draw conclusions based on these results.

Furthermore, due to the limited sample and relatively low response rate, the sample is not a true representation of the population. However, as mentioned before, the research is the groundwork for further research, as the researchers faced questions leading which require further research. This will be discussed later in the report.

CONCLUSION

This research provides insights into the way Dutch consumers between the ages of 20 and 30 are willing to share data. By far, most consumers see sharing data with companies as an increasing part in modern life, even though they do not trust companies to protect their privacy. This research also proves that brand image does influence the way consumers are willing to share data and are willing to provide companies with more data, in exchange for better and more personalized services.

Although the previous statements are proven, it has also become clear that consumers have the feeling they have little control over the data they are sharing with companies and their frequency. This makes it clear that companies will have to give their customers more insights into their data collecting activities, if they want to continue collecting data, without upsetting their customers.

FURTHER RESEARCH

Given the findings of this research, it can be concluded that Dutch consumers are willing to share more data in exchange for more convenience. However, the same consumers also acknowledge that their knowledge about which data are being retrieved lacks. This requires further research into the question: would consumers be still willing to share more data *if they knew* which data is being collected?

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APPENDIX I: SURVEY QUESTIONS

For our pre-master Information Management at Tilburg University, we are conducting research on the correlation between privacy and convenience. We would like to ask you a couple questions about your views on privacy and convenience. The survey should only take about 5 minutes and your responses are completely anonymous. If you have any questions about the survey, please email us: e.oztan@tilburguniversity.edu. We really appreciate your input!

Q1 What is your age?

Q2 I have smart home appliances

Yes (1)

No (2)

Q3 Sharing personal data with companies is an issue for me

Strongly agree (1)

Agree (2)

Neutral (3)

Disagree (4)

Strongly disagree (5)

Q4 Providing personal data with companies is

an increasing part of modern life

Strongly agree (1)

Agree (2)

Neutral (3)

Disagree (4)

Strongly disagree (5)

Q5 I trust that companies will not resell my data

Strongly agree (1)

Agree (2)

Neutral (3)

Disagree (4)

Strongly disagree (5)

Q6 I worry about the security of my personal data gathered by companies

Strongly agree (1)

Agree (2)

Neutral (3)

Disagree (4)

Strongly disagree (5)

Q7

There is no alternative other than to provide personal data if you want to obtain the maximum functionalities of smart home appliances

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neutral (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Q8

I do not mind sharing personal data in return for improved services (e.g. increased functionalities, increased ease of use, less perceived risk)

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neutral (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Q9

I am willing to share more data with companies whose products or services I have used in the past.

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neutral (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Q10 If I distrust a company I will not share any data at all, regardless of the offered product or service.

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neutral (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Q11 I am willing to share more data with a bigger company as oppose to a small company.

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neutral (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Q12 How much control do you feel you have over the data you provide through household appliances?

- A great deal (1)
- A lot (2)
- A moderate amount (3)
- A little (4)
- None at all (5)

Q13 Nowadays, many of our everyday activities are recorded in different ways. How concerned are you about the frequency of sharing data with companies?

- A great deal (1)
 - A lot (2)
 - A moderate amount (3)
 - A little (4)
 - None at all (5)
-